

Reduced Computational Burden of Modulated Model-Predictive Control for Synchronous Reluctance Motor Drive Applications

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Abstract—This paper introduces a novel geometric approach to significantly reduce the computational burden of modulated predictive controllers while maintaining the same steady-state performance and satisfactory dynamic behavior. The proposed geometric method leverages the symmetric properties of the active vectors with respect to the zero vectors in two-level inverters. In addition, the structure of the controller is designed to include the integral of error terms, ensuring zero steady-state tracking error. Several operating points are considered and compared with respect to standard modulated model-predictive control approaches showing similar steady-state performance with a reduced computational effort (about 50%). This enables a broader spectrum of power electronic systems and applications that can be used with the same steady-state performance of standard modulated model-predictive control (M²PC). In addition, the latter option allows for the application of M²PC with high switching-frequency devices, given that a higher sampling frequency leads to an increased switching frequency. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated with a synchronous reluctance motor drive application.

Index Terms—Synchronous reluctance motor, two-level voltage source inverter, modulated model-predictive control, computational burden.

I. INTRODUCTION

Model-predictive control (MPC) methods are widely established as effective control techniques. In the past, the primary barrier to the adoption of MPC in power electronics was its associated computational complexity. Thanks to the readily available hardware and software that handle this difficulty, MPC has become suitable for many applications, offering high dynamic response, multi-objective control, and constraint inclusion. Furthermore, MPC is particularly recommended for

highly non-linear systems where other control methods may not guarantee satisfactory performance.

The classical formulation of MPC, i.e., finite control-set model-predictive control (FCS-MPC), has achieved high robustness, accurate setpoint tracking, and fast dynamics [1, 2]. It is also suitable for multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) systems [3, 4]. However, the non-constant switching frequency of FCS-MPC motivated the investigation of modulated-model predictive control (M²PC) solutions as those presented in [5, 6, 7].

Similar to FCS-MPC, the heavy computational burden of the M²PC algorithms is one of the main obstacles to its use. This prevents reaching high sampling frequencies.

Many solutions have been proposed to reduce the number of candidate voltage vectors, e.g., [8, 9]. In [10], an attempt to reduce the number of calculations of an M²PC was made by employing a deadbeat approach. In [11], the authors tried to decrease the computational workload by using trigonometric identities to identify the best actuating commands showing a 46% reduction in computation time with the same performance. Similar results in simplifying the implementation of an M²PC were achieved in [12]. The regulation of the switching time was achieved by evaluating two active voltage vectors enabling flux control while minimizing the torque ripple of a permanent magnet synchronous machine (PMSM). Other approaches based on M²PC, such as [8], consists of finding the deadbeat solution of the optimization problem to reduce the number of predictions.

This paper aims to take one step further by reducing the execution time of M²PC even more. The proposed M²PC considers a SyRel motor drive application. The selection of active

Fig. 1. 2L-VSI switching states.

vectors is simplified by examining the signs of the corresponding computed duty cycles. This method takes advantage of the symmetry between the active voltage vectors and the zero vectors, resulting in reduced computational steps to compute the duty cycles. The proposed method is assessed by means of simulations and experimental tests with the method presented in [7] to demonstrate the lower computational burden while obtaining comparable system performance.

II. SYREL DRIVE MODEL

Considering the model-based nature of the proposed M²PC, this section provides an accurate representation of the SyRel motor drive. The description of the two-level inverter (2L-VSI) used to drive the motor is reported, along with the experimentally derived and detailed magnetic model representation of the SyRel motor, which is presented in the following.

A. Two-Level Voltage-Source Inverter

The model of a 2L-VSI is given by considering an ideal approach with an instantaneous switching behavior. The output three-phase voltage provided by the 2L-VSI can be expressed as function of the switching signals S_{ga} , S_{gb} , and S_{gc} as

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{V_{dc}}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & 2 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_{ga} \\ S_{gb} \\ S_{gc} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where the switching positions are reported in Tab. I. Given a fixed dc-link voltage V_{dc} , in Fig. 1, the output voltage components are represented for all the switching positions in the stationary reference frame depicting a regular hexagon. In the same figure, the inner circle delimits the linear modulation region. Outside the hexagon area is the overmodulation operation.

The time application of each switching position is determined by using a carrier-based pulse-width modulation (CB-PWM) technique that compares a triangular waveform and

TABLE I
2L-VSI SWITCHING POSITIONS.

\vec{v}_j	\vec{v}_0	\vec{v}_1	\vec{v}_2	\vec{v}_3	\vec{v}_4	\vec{v}_5	\vec{v}_6	\vec{v}_7
$S_{ga}(j)$	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
$S_{gb}(j)$	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1
$S_{gc}(j)$	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1

the reference voltage within a sampling interval. Most of the presented results in the following sections correspond to operations within the linear modulation region.

B. SyRel Machine

The SyRel motor drive model is typically represented in a synchronous reference frame (i.e., dq reference frame) with the d -axis aligned along the rotor position. The continuous-time SyRel motor voltage equation in this frame is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{i}_{dq} = \mathbf{L}^{-1} [\mathbf{v}_{dq} - R_s \mathbf{i}_{dq} - \mathbf{Q} \omega_r \boldsymbol{\psi}_{dq}] \quad (2)$$

In (2), the terms \mathbf{i}_{dq} and $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{dq}$ represent the current and magnetic flux vectors, respectively. The voltage vector $\mathbf{v}_{dq}(j)$ is derived from (1) using the abc -to- dq transformation matrix \mathbf{P} . Here, j represents the voltage vector counter, denoted as $j = [0, 1 \dots 7]$. The stator resistance is represented by the symbol R_s . The rotor electrical speed (i.e., ω_r) is obtained by multiplying the mechanical speed ω_m by the pole pairs (i.e., p). Finally, \mathbf{Q} is the orthogonal rotation matrix $\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, and \mathbf{L}^{-1} is the inverse of the incremental inductance matrix \mathbf{L} described by the self-axis inductance component L_{dd} and L_{qq} , while the cross-coupling inductance components are L_{dq} and L_{qd} .

To complete the description of the SyRel drive model, the equation of the electromagnetic torque T_{em} is expressed as follows

$$T_{em} = \frac{3}{2} p [\psi_d i_q - \psi_q i_d], \quad (3)$$

where the d - and q -axis current and flux components are represented by i_d , i_q , ψ_d , and ψ_q , respectively.

The high non-linear effects of Syrel drive motor drives make the control design non-trivial, especially when considering model-based control methods. For this reason, a magnetic model characterization test was performed to identify accurately self-axis and cross-coupling saturation effects. The former refers to the d -axis and q -axis current saturating the d -axis and q -axis flux, respectively. The latter refers to the d -flux variations due to changes in q -current and vice versa. Therefore, the flux vector has to be assumed as a non-linear function \mathbf{f} of the current vector such as $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{dq} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{i}_{dq})$.

To identify \mathbf{f} , the procedure described in [13] is carried out, and the results are reported in Fig. 2. The flux-versus-current characteristics are reported as level sets of the estimated electromagnetic torque calculated as in (3). Both self- and cross-saturation effects are visible. The maximum torque per ampere (MTPA) trajectory is also identified and reported in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Magnetic model flux maps.

Fig. 3. MTPA trajectory.

III. MODULATED MODEL-PREDICTIVE CONTROL WITH FEWER COMPUTATIONS

A. Modulated Model-Predictive Control

The main idea of classical M²PC formulations is to evaluate a combination of current errors according to (2) and the desired setpoints for each pair of voltage vectors to compute the duty cycles. This involves considering the desired setpoints (i.e., d - and q -current references), the mathematical model of the system, and the feasible voltage vectors.

A two-component evaluation function can be formulated and represented graphically by a hexagon representing the prediction of the system at the next time step using the eight voltage vectors of the 2L-VSI. The solution is selected by

choosing the duty cycles (i.e., d_1, d_2) that meet the following criteria:

$$d_1 \geq 0 \quad (4a)$$

$$d_2 \geq 0 \quad (4b)$$

$$d_1 + d_2 \leq 1 \quad (4c)$$

Integral terms based on the actual error between the feedback and the setpoints are included in the formulation to achieve high robustness to model inaccuracies and variations of parameters. Additionally, feasible solutions are guaranteed even during sudden transients and in the overmodulation region. The approach investigated in [7] selects the solution corresponding to positive duty cycles within the range of zero and one. When this criterion is not met, indicating that the dc-link voltage is insufficient to control the desired operating point, the controller calculates a new reference set as a target lying on the sides of the voltage hexagon to guarantee minimum tracking error.

B. Proposed Modulated Model-Predictive Control

In the method proposed in this manuscript, three out of eight voltage vectors (one zero and two active vectors, i.e., \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2) are considered to calculate the optimum duty cycles. This approach allows to evaluating only three system predictions.

The evaluation function aimed at computing the controller output is defined as

$$\mathbf{g}(j) = \begin{bmatrix} g_d \\ g_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (i_d^* - i_d^{k+1}(j)) + w_d I_d \\ (i_q^* - i_q^{k+1}(j)) + w_d I_q \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where the error tracking terms between the setpoints (i.e., i_d^*, i_q^*) and the current predictions at the next time step $k+1$ (i.e., $i_d^{k+1}(j), i_q^{k+1}(j)$) are computed for $j = [\vec{v}_0, \vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2]$ by discretizing (2). In addition, with T_s as the sampling interval and w_d, w_q as weighting factors tuned with trial-and-error, I_d and I_q represent the d - and q -integrals of the error term of the current in the discrete-time domain, respectively. They are computed as follows:

$$I_d = T_s (i_d^* - i_d^k) + \sum_{\ell=1}^{n-1} (i_d^* - i_d^{k-\ell}) \quad (6a)$$

$$I_q = T_s (i_q^* - i_q^k) + \sum_{\ell=1}^{n-1} (i_q^* - i_q^{k-\ell}). \quad (6b)$$

With these terms, the controller can compensate for any occurring steady-state errors between references and actual d - and q -current components (i.e., i_d^k and i_q^k), with n representing the number of discrete-time samples.

1) *Linear Modulation Region*: Given the above, the duty cycles d_1 and d_2 can be evaluated as a linear combination of the time application of the vectors \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 during a sampling interval as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{G}_{dq} \begin{bmatrix} t_d - g_d(v_{0d}) \\ t_q - g_q(v_{0q}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

Fig. 4. (a) Linear modulation operation. (b) Overmodulation operation.

b
TABLE II

RELATION BETWEEN THE SIGN OF THE DUTY CYCLES AND THE HEXAGON SECTOR (SEC).

	\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2	\vec{v}_2, \vec{v}_3	\vec{v}_3, \vec{v}_4	\vec{v}_4, \vec{v}_5	\vec{v}_5, \vec{v}_6	\vec{v}_6, \vec{v}_1
	Sec_1	Sec_2	Sec_3	Sec_4	Sec_5	Sec_6
d_1	>0	>0	>0	<0	<0	<0
d_2	>0	<0	<0	<0	>0	>0

where

$$\mathbf{G}_{dq} = \begin{bmatrix} g_d(v_{1d}) - g_d(v_{0d}) & g_d(v_{2d}) - g_d(v_{0d}) \\ g_q(v_{1q}) - g_q(v_{0q}) & g_q(v_{2q}) - g_q(v_{0q}) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

In (8), $g_d(v_{1d})$ and $g_q(v_{1q})$ represent the d and q components of (5), assuming that \vec{v}_1 was applied. In the same way, $g_d(v_{2d})$ and $g_q(v_{2q})$ represent the d and q components computed by (5), when \vec{v}_2 was applied. The terms $g_d(v_{0d})$ and $g_q(v_{0q})$ represents the d and q coordinates of (5) calculated for \vec{v}_0 . Finally, in (7), t_d and t_q are the d and q coordinates that express the zero-steady state error target which is set to zero at steady-state and during linear modulation region. In this case, the duty cycles are not referred to specific voltage vectors as in [7], but, for the case analyzed, they are always referred to \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 . As a consequence, positive and negative solutions for (7) in the range $[-1, +1]$ represent feasible solutions. A graphical interpretation of negative duty cycles solution can be explained by Fig. 4. The zero steady-state target is reached by applying \vec{v}_1 for a fraction of the switching interval. The solution computed for d_1 can be represented by the segment connecting $g(\vec{v}_0)$ and $g(\vec{v}_1)$. The overlap of the two segments indicates that the corresponding duty cycle is positive. On the other hand, the solution found for d_2 is represented on the negative direction of the segment connecting $g(\vec{v}_0)$ and $g(\vec{v}_2)$, indicating a negative duty cycle. Considering the same setpoint reference, it is possible to define a table to express the relationship between d_1 and d_2 and the actual hexagon sector of the set $([\vec{v}_1, \vec{v}_2], [\vec{v}_2, \vec{v}_3], \dots, [\vec{v}_6, \vec{v}_1])$, (see Tab. II). Note that the time application of the zero vector is

$$d_0 = 1 - [d_1 + d_2]. \quad (9)$$

Fig. 5. Proposed M²PC control scheme.

For a generic time instant, the application of \vec{v}_1 , \vec{v}_2 , and \vec{v}_0 to (5) shape a triangle, rotating at the synchronous speed of the motor in the g_d, g_q plane. The duty cycles calculated as in (7) are characterized by a periodic pattern. They vary according to the relative position between the origin of the axis and the triangle. In particular, if the $(0,0)$ coordinates are located inside the triangle formed by \vec{v}_1 , \vec{v}_2 , and \vec{v}_0 , the duties d_1 and d_2 are positive. As the triangle rotates, the duty cycles change periodically, alternating between both positive, one positive and one negative, and both negative, with the signs of d_1 and d_2 inverted accordingly.

2) *Overmodulation Region*: When the saturation of the voltage command occurs the zero steady-state error is not achievable at the next time step. The controller aims to achieve the control output by selecting a new target lying on the sides of the hexagon.

The proposed formulation, however, is not suitable for evaluating the target coordinates. Referring to the situation represented in Fig. 4(b), applying the criteria described in [7] (i.e., finding the intersection between the line passing through $g(\vec{v}_1)$, $g(\vec{v}_2)$ and the line passing through the points $[0, 0]$ and $g(\vec{v}_0)$), result in an incorrect solution. In fact such a solution (i.e., the red dot represented in Fig. 4(b)), will move the system away from the desired solution (i.e., the yellow dot represented in Fig. 4(b) indicating zero tracking error). Ideally, the target coordinates in the g_d, g_q plane should be positioned between the $g(\vec{v}_0)$ coordinates and the origin of the axis. When this criterion is not met, the controller performs a re-formulation of the target coordinates by evaluating the symmetric point with respect to the point achieved by the application of \vec{v}_0 as follows:

$$\bar{t}_d = 2g_d(v_{0d}) - t_d \quad (10a)$$

$$\bar{t}_q = 2g_q(v_{0q}) - t_q \quad (10b)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, simulation results for the proposed M²PC are shown. The system is simulated using the Matlab/Simulink environment, based on the model described in Section II, which includes self- and cross-saturation phenomena through the use of look-up tables (LUTs). The overall control diagram is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 6. Setpoints tracking at low modulation index.

Fig. 7. Calculated duty cycles with the proposed OT-M²PC.

A. Low Modulation Index Results

The simulation are conducted considering 600 V dc-link voltage, $\omega_m = 500$ rpm set by the prime mover, and the sampling frequency of 10 kHz set for the controller. The d and q -current step response are shown in Fig. 6 in blue and red. The current vector setpoint was chosen on the MTPA trajectory (see Fig. 3) corresponding to a torque command of 7 Nm. The same operating point is shown for the control strategy introduced in [7]. It is possible to deduce that similar settling times are observable. In particular, the proposed strategy presents a slightly faster rising time on the q -current axis response. This is because the lack of knowledge of all the possible current predictions makes the output of the proposed controller sub-optimal.

Regarding the step response curves shown in Fig. 6, the duty cycles computed with the method described in this manuscript and the ones achieved by considering the methods in [7] are compared in Fig. 7. It is noticeable that both the d_1 and d_2 waveforms periodically overlap. This happens when both d_1 and d_2 are positive, i.e., when the optimal vectors according to [7] are \vec{v}_1 and \vec{v}_2 . In other cases, e.g., when the vector \vec{v}_4 and \vec{v}_5 should be applied, both duty cycles result negative. In other cases, when vectors such as \vec{v}_4 and \vec{v}_5 should be applied, at least one of the two duty cycle waveforms matches between the two methods.

For the same step response results, a comparison was conducted to show how differently the two controllers behave during transients. In particular, the evolution of both the hexagon and triangle over time are shown in Fig. 8 for two-time instants (i.e., t_1 and t_2 , where $t_2 > t_1$). It is possible to notice that (10) allows for re-calculating the original target (i.e., red dots) such

Fig. 8. Triangle evolution over time.

Fig. 9. Phase-currents tracking.

Fig. 10. Phase-current Harmonic spectra.

that the zero steady-state error is achievable (green dots) in a few time steps. In addition, lower prediction errors between the triangle and the hexagon are observed at $t = t_1$. That is because when the operation changes from lower to higher currents the higher error in the prediction at lower inductance makes the controller output more aggressive with the target identified outside the actual boundaries. This is not an issue because the logic of the cascaded CB-PWM stage ensures the saturation of the voltage command.

The phase-current tracking is shown in Fig. 9 with the a - and b -phase current harmonic spectra in Fig. 10.

B. High Modulation Index Results

Further simulation results are shown for the same settings described in the previous simulation result subsection, but at another operating point (i.e., $T_{em} = 7$ Nm and $\omega_m = 1500$ rpm). In these conditions, the drive operates at a higher modulation index, and the d - and q -current setpoint tracking is shown in Fig. 11 for both the proposed controller and the

Fig. 11. Setpoint trackings at high modulation index.

Fig. 12. (Left) Hexagon evolution [7] and (Right) triangle evolution over time for the proposed controller.

standard M²PC. The proposed controller exhibits a slower response compared to the standard M²PC. This behavior is attributed to the suboptimal target coordinates calculated in these conditions, resulting from the lack of system prediction in all the feasible voltage vectors. The deterioration of the transient performance at a higher modulation index is the trade-off for having a computationally more efficient M²PC algorithm.

The comparison of the hexagon evolution over time and the triangle evolution over time is reported in Fig. 12(left) and 12(right), respectively. Notably, the trajectory of the target coordinates (i.e., green dots) in Fig. 12(left) follows a shorter path.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results of the proposed controllers are presented in this section.

The control platform used to control the prime mover and the SyRel motor drive is based on the setup introduced in [14]. The platform is based on a Microzed board from Avnet, a low-cost development board based on the Xilinx Zynq-7000 which combines a DSP and an FPGA device. The setup includes several expansion boards for interfacing with sensors and transceivers. One of the boards is aimed to host fiber optics channels to send the switching signals to the converter. A second board hosts the Analog-to-digital converters (ADC). Another extension board provides an interface for absolute/incremental encoders.

Fig. 13. Setpoint tracking on the d -axis. (Top) Proposed M²PC. (Bottom) M²PC described in [7].

The rotational speed is set by a prime mover, while the SyRel motor is operated under current control. The phase-current vector is measured and transformed into the rotor-oriented reference frame by considering the mechanical angle read by an absolute encoder with 21 bits accuracy, and the Clarke and Park transformations. The dc-link voltage is measured via an ADC stage (16 bits accuracy) and read by the digital signal processor (DSP). Once the evaluation function (5) is calculated, the resulting duty cycles are then transformed into the three-phase reference frame (i.e., abc). A carrier-based pulse-width modulation (CB-PWM) stage is executed by a field-programmable gate array (FPGA) to generate the gate signal for the 2L-VSI.

The implemented control strategy is tested in the current-control mode for fixed-speed applications. The rotational speed is set to 500 rpm by the prime mover. The dc-link voltage source is set to $V_{dc} = 300$ V using a dc power supply, and the sampling frequency is set to $f_s = 10$ kHz. Two current measurements, the dc-link voltage, and the angle detected by an absolute encoder are recorded. The switching commands are sent to the 2L-VSI through fiber optic signals (see Fig. 5).

The d - and q -current reference tracking for the controller introduced in this manuscript and the one introduced in [7] are compared in Fig. 13(top) and 13(bottom), respectively. Both strategies show comparable performance. Similar rising edges can be observed for both controllers on both axes. Note that the references of the d and q -axis are not simultaneous. For the same test, the computed duty cycles are shown in the synchronous reference frame in Fig. 14 from where the magnetic axis duty cycles calculated and represented in Fig. 15 for both the controllers. It is possible to match the duty cycle waveforms in the last figure. Finally, the measured waveforms and the corresponding references are shown in Fig. 16 and ??

Fig. 14. abc duty cycles calculation. (Top) Proposed M²PC, (Bottom) M²PC [7]

Fig. 16. Measured phase current. (Top) Proposed M²PC. (Bottom) M²PC described in [7].

Fig. 15. abc duty cycles calculation. (Top) Proposed M²PC. (Bottom) M²PC described in [7].

Fig. 17. (a) d and q step response comparison at higher modulation index. (b) Duty cycles.

for the two controllers.

A further test at a higher modulation index (i.e., above 0.9) is performed to show the d - and q -current step response for both controllers. The higher modulation index test is conducted to evaluate the controllers' performance under more challenging operating conditions. In this case, a 7 Nm torque reference is considered and the resulting d - and q -current setpoints are calculated based on the MTPA (see Fig. 3). As observed in the simulation results, the q -axis step response is affected by cross-coupling effects, leading to an undershoot when the d -axis command changes. The d -axis dynamic is not

affected due to the inherent higher inductance as typical in SyRel motors. In addition, the same steady-state performance can be observed for both controllers.

The computational complexity of the proposed M²PC controller is computed and compared with the method in [7]. The measured turnaround time is shown in Fig. 18. It can be observed that the standard M²PC takes about 6.4% of the sampling interval (i.e., 10 kHz) to execute the control algorithm. On the other hand, the turnaround time of the proposed controller (i.e., the white reference trend waveform) is measured as 2.8% of the sampling interval.

Fig. 18. M²PC turnaround time.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces the proposed M²PC and demonstrates its effectiveness through simulations and experiments. The results show a substantial reduction in computational effort without compromising the steady-state performance of the system. The dynamic performance of the proposed controller was compared with another solution recently proposed in the literature. The results have shown similar dynamic performance and equivalent current distortions at lower modulation indexes.

However, it was observed that at higher modulation indexes, the presence of cross-coupling terms worsens the performance of the quadrature axis. Despite this effect, the proposed M²PC still maintains satisfactory performance.

These results were achieved by applying the proposed M²PC to a SyRel motor drive application and using accurate system modeling. The reduced computational complexity allows for the implementation of M²PC (a) on low-cost control platforms, and (b) at higher sampling frequencies. The former enables the use of this method in a wider range of power electronic systems and applications. The latter enables the use of M²PC with high switching-frequency devices as a higher sampling frequency results in a higher switching frequency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Riccio, P. Karamanakos, S. Odhano, M. Tang, M. D. Nardo, and P. Zanchetta, "A direct model predictive control strategy for high-performance synchronous reluctance motor drives," in *2021 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, 2021, pp. 4704–4710.
- [2] J. Riccio, P. Karamanakos, S. Odhano, M. Tang, M. Di Nardo, and P. Zanchetta, "Direct model predictive control of synchronous reluctance motor drives," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 1054–1063, 2023.
- [3] S. R. Di Salvo, M. Bulzi, J. Riccio, R. Leuzzi, P. Zanchetta, and N. Anglani, "Model predictive control of a double stage AC-DC converter for grid-interface of vanadium flow batteries," in *2021 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, 2021, pp. 1895–1901.
- [4] J. Riccio, L. Rovere, S. Odhano, M. Di Nardo, and P. Zanchetta, "Model-predictive control of open-end winding synchronous reluctance motor drives," in *2022 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, 2022, pp. 1–8.

- [5] E. Fuentes, C. A. Silva, and R. M. Kennel, "MPC implementation of a quasi-time-optimal speed control for a PMSM drive, with inner modulated-FS-MPC torque control," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 6, pp. 3897–3905, 2016.
- [6] J. Riccio, S. A. Odhano, and P. Zanchetta, "Sensorless and modulated model-predictive control for a doubly fed induction machine," in *2019 21st European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE '19 ECCE Europe)*, Sep. 2019, pp. P.1–P.10.
- [7] J. Riccio, P. Karamanakos, S. Odhano, M. Tang, M. Di Nardo, G. Tresca, and P. Zanchetta, "Modulated model-predictive integral control applied to a synchronous reluctance motor drive," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, pp. 1–1, 2023.
- [8] C. Xia, T. Liu, T. Shi, and Z. Song, "A simplified finite-control-set model-predictive control for power converters," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 991–1002, 2014.
- [9] I. Harbi, M. Abdelrahem, M. Ahmed, and R. Kennel, "Reduced-complexity model predictive control with online parameter assessment for a grid-connected single-phase multilevel inverter," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 19, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/19/7997>
- [10] W. Benjamim, I. Jlassi, and A. J. M. Cardoso, "A computationally efficient model predictive current control of synchronous reluctance motors based on hysteresis comparators," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/11/3/379>
- [11] E. T. Andrew, K. Ahmed, and D. Holliday, "A new modulated model predictive current controller with reduced computational burden," in *2021 9th International Conference on Smart Grid (icSmartGrid)*, 2021, pp. 254–258.
- [12] A. Nasr, C. Gu, G. Buticchi, S. Bozhko, and C. Gerada, "A low-complexity modulated model predictive torque and flux control strategy for PMSM drives without weighting factor," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1305–1316, 2023.
- [13] E. Armando, R. I. Bojoi, P. Guglielmi, G. Pellegrino, and M. Pastorelli, "Experimental identification of the magnetic model of synchronous machines," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 2116–2125, 2013.
- [14] A. Galassini, G. Lo Calzo, A. Formentini, C. Gerada, P. Zanchetta, and A. Costabeber, "uCube: Control platform for power electronics," in *2017 IEEE Workshop on Electrical Machines Design, Control and Diagnosis (WEMDCD)*, 2017, pp. 216–221.